

Milestone 9.5: Updated list of services available via TNA

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Work package n°	9
Milestone / Deliverable n°	MS44 – 9.5
Lead beneficiary	CNR
Document Type	Document
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	M44
Actual delivery date	M44
Version	0
Reviewed by	Project Office
Accepted by	
Comments	

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1 Introduction

This document is prepared in the context of the ATMO-ACCESS project (Solutions for Sustainable Access to Prepared in the context of the ATMO-ACCESS project (Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities), which supports transnational, physical, and remote access to first-class operational European atmospheric research facilities, this document offers an updated list of the services available within the project.

Fifty-two facilities belonging to ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS Research Infrastructures (RIs) have been participating in the TNA activities since the beginning of the project, while another 9 joined the project as TNA providers in 2023, bringing the overall number of facilities to 61, namely:

- 29 Observational Facilities (OF), ground-based stations for long-term observations of atmospheric constituents that deliver long-term data based on a regular measurement schedule and common operation standards.
- 14 Simulation Chamber Facilities (SC), used to perform dedicated experiments under controlled conditions.
- 5 Mobile Facilities (MF).
- 13 Central Laboratories (CL), of which 4 are singular CL and 9 are co-located with OF (7), CF (1) and MF (1).

This document includes the research, innovation, and technical services offered by the new facilities selected for TNA provision under ATMO-ACCESS, as well as the new training services developed in WP4, “Developing and optimally integrating joint training services.” New services are included in blue font.

This updates the list of services available for physical, remote, and hybrid access within the project, as included and described in MS41/9.2. It also prepares for deliverable D9.4, which will provide the final list of TNA services contributing to the RI’s catalogue of services with updated, detailed information and descriptions for each of them.

2 ATMO-ACCESS Updated list of services available via TNA

Facility type	FACILITY (short name)	LOCATION	SERVICE NAME	TYPE OF SERVICE	TYPE OF ACCESS
Obs.	AGORA	Spain, Granada	Campaigns for Aerosol-Cloud Interaction Research	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs.	AGORA	Spain, Granada	Experiments for Aerosol-Cloud Interaction Research	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs.	AGORA	Spain, Granada	Instrument Testing and Intercomparison Campaigns	Research service	Physical
Obs.	AGORA	Spain, Granada	Young Scientists Training	Training service	Physical, remote
Obs.	AGORA	Spain, Granada	Training for Companies	Training service	Physical
Obs.	AGORA	Spain, Granada	Support to private innovation	Technical service	Physical
Obs	ARN	Huelva, Spain	Instrument Testing and Intercomparison Campaigns in accordance with ACTRIS and ICOS requirements	Research service	Physical
Obs	ARN	Huelva, Spain	Experimental campaigns for atmospheric characterization	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs	ARN	Huelva, Spain	Service for training through hands-on-instrument operative and data analysis	Training service	Physical, remote
Obs.	ATMOS	Athens, Greece	Access to services of the ATHens MOnitoring Supersite	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	BCN	Barcelona, Spain	Access to services of the BCN Atmospheric Research network	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	CAO	Agia Marina Xyliatou, Cyprus	Access to services of the Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	Methane stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D-CH}_4$)	Research service / Technical service	Remote
Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	Methane clumped isotope analysis ($\Delta^{13}\text{C-D-CH}_4$, $\Delta\text{-D-D-CH}_4$)	Research service / Technical service	Remote
Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	Carbon monoxide stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O-CO}$)	Research service / Technical service	Remote
Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	Hydrogen stable isotope analysis ($\delta\text{D-H}_2$)	Research service / Technical service	Remote

Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	In-situ, column integrated, vertical profiling and spatial atmospheric observations	Data, research, technical, innovation, training service	Physical, remote
Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	Cloud radar calibration	Research, Technical service, Training	Physical
Obs.	CESAR	Lopik, the Netherlands	Trace gas remote sensing intercomparison	Research, Technical service, Training	Physical
Obs	CIAO	CNR-IMAA, Tito (Potenza), Italy	Training on lidar data analysis, SCC and on technical aspects of lidar systems	Research service / Technical service/Training	Physical, remote
Obs	CIAO	CNR-IMAA, Tito (Potenza), Italy	Intercomparison of lidar systems at CIAO	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs	CIAO	CNR-IMAA, Tito (Potenza), Italy	Access and integration of data using different active, passive and in-situ instruments at CIAO	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs	CIAO	CNR-IMAA, Tito (Potenza), Italy	Laboratory characterization of instruments and blocks	Research service / Technical service/Training	Physical
Obs	CIAO	CNR-IMAA, Tito (Potenza), Italy	Testing and building lidar configurations	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs	CVAO	Calhau, (Sao Vicente), Cape Verde	Data access, In-situ intercomparison, and calibration for aerosol physical properties and chemical composition	Data/ research/ technology/training/Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	CVAO	Mindelo, (Sao Vicente), Cape Verde	Cal/Val campaigns in support of satellite atmospheric missions	Data/ Research Service	Physical, remote
Obs	CVAO	Mindelo, (Sao Vicente), Cape Verde	Access to the services of the ARS and CRS facility, CVAO, Mindelo, Cape Verde	Data/Research Service	Physical, remote
Obs	CVAO	Mindelo, (Sao Vicente), Cape Verde	Instrument Deployment and Testing	Technical Service	Physical
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Monte Cimone (Modena)	Calibration of chemiluminescence NOx analyzers at CMN-PV	Technical service	Physical, remote

Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Monte Cimone (Modena)	Calibration of ozone analysers	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Bologna	Calibration of ozone analysers	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, S. Pietro Capofiume (Bologna)	DOAS measurement facility	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Bologna	Calibration of chemiluminescence analysers at CMN-PV	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Monte Cimone (Modena)	In-situ intercomparison for near-surface gas and aerosol analysers	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Bologna	In-situ intercomparison for near-surface gas and aerosol analysers	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, S. Pietro Capofiume (Bologna)	In-situ intercomparison for near-surface gas and aerosol analysers	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Monte Cimone (Modena)	Analysis of atmospheric process by in-situ "near-surface" observations at a high mountain site	Research service / Training service / Data service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, Bologna	Analysis of atmospheric process by in-situ "near-surface" observations at an urban site	Research service / Training service / Data service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Monte Cimone - Po Valley (CMN-PV)	CNR-ISAC, Italy, S. Pietro Capofiume (Bologna)	Analysis of atmospheric process by in-situ "near-surface" observations at a rural site	Research service / Training service / Data service	Physical, remote
Obs.	CO-PDD	Clermont-Ferrand, France	Access to services of the Cézeaux-Aulnat Opme Puy de Dôme station	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	EVASO	Evora, Portugal	Access to services of the Evora Atmospheric Science Observatory	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	FKL	Finokalia, Crete, Greece	Access to services of the Finokalia station	Research service / Technical service	Physical

Obs.	FMI PAL-SOD	Muonio, Finland	Access to services of the Pallas-Sodankylä Atmosphere-Ecosystem Supersite	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	HTM	Forest in southern Sweden	Access to services of the HTM station	Research service / Training service	Physical, remote
Obs.	ISAF - Izaña Observatory (IZO)	Spain, Izaña (Tenerife)	ISAF-Cal Calibration and intercomparison of photometers at IZO	Research, training, technical development	Physical, remote
Obs.	ISAF- Izaña Observatory (IZO)	Spain, Izaña (Tenerife)	ISAF-Obs Atmospheric observations in free-troposphere conditions at IZO	Research, campaigns, intercomparisons	Physical (once installed also remote)
Obs.	JFJ	Jungfrauoch, Switzerland	Access to services of the JFJ station	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	Melpitz	Germany, Melpitz	Aerosol physico-chemical properties (ground and vertical)	Data, research, technological, innovation, training service	Physical, remote
Obs.	NAOK	Košetice, Czech Republic	Access to services of the National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	OPAR	La Réunion, France	Access to services of the Observatoire de Physique de l'Atmosphère à La Réunion	Research service / Technical service	Physical
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Instrument Testing & Validation	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Algorithm Testing & Validation (RS)	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Cal/Val experiments in support of satellite atmospheric missions (RS)	Research Service	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Provision of near real-time aerosol products for model applications (RS)	Research Service	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Aerosol-cloud-radiation case studies (RS)	Research service	Physical, remote

Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Training on lidar data analysis and data systems (RS)	Research service / Technical service/Training	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Instrument testing (IS)	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Aerosol and trace gases (IS) measurements	Research	Physical, remote
Obs.	PANGEA (AKY)	NOA, Greece	Training on near real-time in-situ measurements (IS)	Research service / Technical service/Training	Physical, remote
Obs.	RADO	Magurele, Romania	Aerosol-clouds-radiation studies	Research service	Physical, remote
Obs.	RADO	Magurele, Romania	Cal/Val campaigns in support of satellite atmospheric missions	Research Service	Physical, remote
Obs.	RADO	Magurele, Romania	Training	Training service	Physical, remote
Obs.	RADO	Magurele, Romania	Deployment of mobile reference aerosol Lidar for short-term campaigns	Technical service	Physical
Obs.	RADO	Magurele, Romania	Testing of aerosol Lidar prototypes	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Intercomparison of instruments for cloud in situ, LWC	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Sampling support	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Instrument operation	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Training	research	physical
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Cable car profiles	Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Data analysis and preparation	data, research	remote

Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Regional to global backwards modelling with ECMWF-FLEXPART model	Data, research service	remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Time-series of atmospheric boundary layer heights derived from ceilometer observations	Data, research	remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Measurement of boundary layer wind and turbulence profiles	Technical service, data, research	remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Specific weather forecast for Mt. Hoher Sonnblick	Information service	remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Climate scenarios for Mt. Hoher Sonnblick	Information service	remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Meteorological consulting	Information service	remote
Obs.	Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	ZAMG, Austria, Rauris (Mt. Hoher Sonnblick)	Avalanche advice and avalanche warning service	Information service	remote
Obs.	SIRTA	Plateau de Saclay, France	Access to services of the SIRTA - Site Instrumental de Recherche par Télédétection Atmosphérique	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	SMEAR II	Juupajoki, Finland	Access to services of the Station for Measuring Ecosystem - Atmosphere Relations II	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	SMEAR Estonia	Järvselja, Estonia	Access to services of the Station for Measuring Ecosystem - Atmosphere Relations Estonia	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	WOS	Warsaw, Poland	Access to services of the Warsaw Observatory Station	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Obs.	Villum	Station Nord, Greenland; Kingdom of Denmark	Long term monitoring of Arctic haze, and campaign studies of Arctic atmospheric chemistry and physics.	Research, campaigns, intercomparisons	Physical
Obs.	WOPAS	Wroclaw, Poland	Campaigns for urban air quality	Research	Physical, remote
Obs.	WOPAS	Wroclaw, Poland	Atmospheric boundary layer structure	Research	Physical, remote

Obs.	WOPAS	Wroclaw, Poland	Allergic pollen measurements	Research	Physical, remote
Obs.	WOPAS	Wroclaw, Poland	Mobile measurements of air quality and meteorological and biometeorological parameters	research/technical	Physical, remote
Obs.	WOPAS	Wroclaw, Poland	Instrument Testing and Intercomparison Campaigns	research/technical	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	1) Training on state of the art offline and online analytical instrumentation 2) Training on good chamber practice	Training service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	Scientific research on tropospheric multiphase processes under controlled chamber conditions	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	Newly developed instrumentation testing, (inter)calibrations and intercomparisons	Innovation service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	Support for instrument (innovation) development	Technological service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	Scientific research on cloud-microphysics - turbulence interaction	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	Testing of (new) instrumentation, and instrument intercomparisons under turbulent conditions	Technical and innovation service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ACD-C / LACIS-T	Germany, Leipzig, at TROPOS 51.35°N, 12.43°E, 120 m a.s.l.	Training on LACIS-T including state-of-the-art instrumentation	Training service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	AIDA	Karlsruhe, Germany	Scientific exploration at the AIDA atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical

Sim. Chamber	AURA	Aarhus University, Langelandsgade 140, DK-8000 Aarhus	Experiments in Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	Research service	Mainly physical
Sim. Chamber	CESAM	Créteil, France	Scientific exploration at the CESAM atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	ChAMBRe	INFN, Italy, Genoa	Bioaerosol characterization	Research service, technical service, innovation	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	ChAMBRe	INFN, Italy, Genoa	Testing and characterization of bioaerosol monitors/sensors	Research service, technical service, innovation	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	ChAMBRe	INFN, Italy, Genoa	Measurement of aerosol optical properties	Research service, technical service, innovation	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	ChAMBRe	INFN, Italy, Genoa	Testing of samplers and gas/aerosol monitors	Research service, technical service, innovation	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	ChAMBRe	INFN, Italy, Genoa	Design, organization and execution of custom experiments	Research service, technical service, innovation	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	ESC-Q-UAIC	Iași, Romania	Scientific exploration at the ESC-Q-UAIC environmental simulation chamber	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	EUPHORE	Paterna, Spain	Scientific research at the EUPHORE atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical (preferred) remote access
Sim. Chamber	EUPHORE	Paterna, Spain	Intercomparison and performance assessment of instrumentation at the EUPHORE atmospheric simulation chamber	Research, Technological service, Innovative service	Physical (preferred) remote access
Sim. Chamber	EUPHORE	Paterna, Spain	Technical and innovation services at the EUPHORE atmospheric simulation chamber	Technological service, Innovative service	Physical (preferred) remote access
Sim. Chamber	HELIOS	Orléans, France	Scientific exploration at the HELIOS atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	IASC	Cork, Ireland	Scientific exploration at the IASC atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical

Sim. Chamber	KASCs Kuopio atmospheric simulation chambers	Yliopistonranta 1, 70210 Kuopio, Finland	Atmospheric simulation chamber investigations	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	MAC	Manchester, United Kingdom	Scientific exploration at the MAC atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	PACS-C2	Villigen, Switzerland	Scientific exploration at the PACS-CS Atmospheric Chemistry Simulation Chambers	Research service	Physical access preferred, remote access can also be provided
Sim. Chamber	PACS-C2	Villigen, Switzerland	Newly developed instrumentation testing and intercomparisons at PACS-C2	Innovation service	Physical
Sim. Chamber	QUAREC	Wuppertal, Germany	Investigation of kinetics and mechanism of gas-phase reaction systems	Research service, training service, technical service	Physical, remote
Sim. Chamber	QUAREC	Wuppertal, Germany	Testing of instruments for measuring air quality	Research service, technical service, innovation service	Physical (preferred) and remote
Sim. Chamber	SAPHIR	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Wilhelm-Johnen-Str., 52428 Jülich, Germany	Scientific exploration at the SAPHIR atmospheric simulation chamber	Research service	Physical access is preferred, remote access can also be provided
Mobile	AMP	Sosnowiec, Poland	Access to services of the ACTRIS-Poland Mobile LAB In-situ measurements	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Mobile	AMP	Sosnowiec Poland	Access to services of the ACTRIS-Poland Mobile LAB remote sensing measurements	Research service / Technical service	Physical, remote
Mobile	FCoMLab	Helsinki and Tampere, Finland	Access to services of the FCoMLab Mobile Exploratory Platform	Research service	Physical, remote
Mobile	FORTH-MSC	Patras (Greece) but can be moved to any location in Europe.	Testing / intercomparisons of new instruments.	Technical service	Physical, remote
Mobile	FORTH-MSC	Patras (Greece) but can be moved to any	Characterization of sources and their atmospheric evolution.	Research service	Physical, remote

		location in Europe.			
Mobile	FORTH-MSC	Patras (Greece) but can be moved to any location in Europe.	Chemical aging experiments for primary and secondary organic aerosol.	Research service	Physical, remote
Mobile	LACROS	Leipzig, Germany	Instrument Testing & Validation	Technical service	Physical, remote
Mobile	LACROS	Leipzig, Germany	Algorithm Testing & Validation	Research service	Physical, remote
Mobile	LACROS	Leipzig, Germany	Deployment at user-defined Location	Research service	Physical, remote
Mobile	LACROS	Leipzig, Germany	Case studies of aerosol-cloud-dynamics-precipitation interactions	Research service	Physical, remote
Mobile	LACROS	Leipzig, Germany	Training	Training service	Physical, remote
Mobile	USRL	Nicosia, Cyprus	Access to services of the USRL Mobile Exploratory Platform	Research service	Physical, remote
Central Lab	CiGAS-CH	Switzerland, Dübendorf [Zürich]	Organic trace gases (VOC/halocarbons)	Research service, technical service	Remote
Central Lab	CiGAS-CH	Switzerland, Dübendorf [Zürich]	N ₂ O isotopes	Research service, technical service	Remote
Central Lab	CiGAS-CH	Switzerland, Dübendorf [Zürich]	@VOC@ QA tool	Training service	Remote
Central Lab	ICOS-ATC	Plateau de Saclay, Paris suburb, France	Access to services of the ICOS-ATC Central Laboratory	Research service, technical service	Physical
Central Lab	PACC	Prague, Czech republic	Calibration, Intercomparisons, Audits and Training	Research service, technical service, training service	Physical, remote
Central Lab	WCCAP	Leipzig, Germany	Calibration, Intercomparisons, Audits and Training	Research service, technical service	Physical, remote

3 Description of the services provided by the new facilities

3.1 Services provided by the WOPAS - Wrocław Observatory Platform for Atmospheric Studies

SERVICE 1 - Campaigns for urban air quality	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>Measurement campaigns enabling the determination of atmospheric aerosol properties using in situ measurements (aethalometer, nephelometer, ultrafine and fine particle distribution spectrometers) and remote sensing techniques (high-power aerosol lidar, photometers) allow for the characterization of aerosol properties. These measurements will be supplemented with data on the concentrations of gaseous pollutants, such as NO_x (NO, NO₂), ozone, suspended particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}), and aerosol chemical composition analysis based on gravimetric measurements.</p> <p>At the WOPAS platform, comprehensive meteorological measurements are conducted, including the radiation balance in the longwave and shortwave ranges, precipitation intensity and type using an optical disdrometer, wind speed and direction, and temperature gradient measurements up to 14 m above ground level on a meteorological tower. Additionally, the structure of the lower part of the boundary layer is studied using SODAR.</p> <p>Furthermore, the WOPAS team has extensive experience in modeling atmospheric processes using models such as WRF, WRF-Chem, EMEP, u_EMEP, and ADMS. Methods for applying machine learning in air quality modeling are also being developed.</p> <p>The campaigns provide data for urban air quality assessments, enabling evidence-based decisions for e.g. health impact assessment, air quality management, and deeper insight into processes favoring haze events.</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Anetta Drzeniecka-Osiadacz (anetta.drzeniecka-osiadacz@uwr.edu.pl) Tymoteusz Sawiński (Tymoteusz.sawinski@uwr.edu.pl)

SERVICE 2 – Atmospheric boundary layer structure	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>The atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is one of the fundamental part of the atmosphere influencing e.g. air quality, substance transport, etc. In middle latitudes, during radiative weather conditions, it is characterized by typical variability resulting from changes in the radiative balance. Despite the importance of proper parameterization of the boundary layer, particularly in determining the depth of the mixing layer, errors generated by meteorological models can reach up to 100%. Therefore, it is especially crucial to develop an appropriate methodology to fully describe the dynamics of the ABL.</p> <p>The goal of the measurement experiment is to integrate lidar, sodar, drone, and ground-based measurements to verify assumptions regarding the depth of the mixing height and validate results from atmospheric models. At WOPAS, continuous measurements are conducted using high-power aerosol lidar, monostatic Doppler minisodar, vertical profile measurements with a prototype measurement head installed on a drone, and comprehensive meteorological observations. The integration of multiple measurement methods ensures a robust understanding of ABL dynamics, aiding in the refinement of meteorological models and their outputs, particularly in urban and rural settings</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical and Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Anetta Drzeniecka-Osiadacz (anetta.drzeniecka-osiadacz@uwr.edu.pl) Tymoteusz Sawiński (Tymoteusz.sawinski@uwr.edu.pl)

SERVICE 3 – Instrument Testing and Intercomparison Campaigns	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Technical service

SERVICE DESCRIPTION	Intercomparison campaigns. Comparison, testing, exploitation of any measurement devices with WOPAS instruments that follow ACTRIS protocols (both in-situ and remote-sensing aerosols measurements) or meteorological equipment. Campaigns can include the testing of usefulness for mobile measurements. These campaigns help users ensure compliance with measuring standards, improve device calibration, and build capacity through hands-on experience.
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, private sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Anetta Drzeniecka-Osiadacz (anetta.drzeniecka-osiadacz@uwr.edu.pl) Tymoteusz Sawiński (Tymoteusz.sawinski@uwr.edu.pl)

SERVICE 4 – Allergic pollen measurements

TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	Measurement campaigns aim to analyze the variability of plant pollen in the urban atmosphere and its coexistence with air pollutants to determine potential adverse health effects. The planned measurements will include in-situ observations (using the Swissens Poleno Jupiter automatic pollen analyzer and the Burkard-type manual pollen trap) as well as lidar measurements utilizing the fluorescence channel.
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, remote

TARGET USERS	Academia,
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	Pollen season
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Anetta Drzeniecka-Osiadacz (anetta.drzeniecka-osiadacz@uwr.edu.pl) Małgorzata Werner malgorzata.werner@uwr.edu.pl
SERVICE 5 – Mobile measurements of air quality and meteorological and biometeorological parameters	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service, technical service, innovation service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>An important supplement to stationary measurements can be mobile measurements of atmospheric environment parameters (e.g. air pollution, meteorological and biometeorological parameters, etc.). Such measurements can be performed using drones, car platforms, bicycles and other similar vehicles, as well as on foot. The experience of the team of the WOPAS indicates that the results of such measurements can be used, among others, for recognition of spatial variability of measured parameters on a local and micro scale, recognition of variability of measured parameters outside the area covered by stationary measurements, indication of areas particularly exposed to hazards related to the atmospheric environment.</p> <p>Within these services, the WOPAS team offers both urban oriented measurements and measurements in mountain areas. Moreover during campaigns the usefulness of sensors can be tested. Mobile measurements provide unique insights into spatial and temporal variability of atmospheric parameters, identifying hotspots and supporting tailored mitigation strategies in both urban and challenging mountainous environments.</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, private sector, Public sector

SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Anetta Drzeniecka-Osiadacz (anetta.drzeniecka-osiadacz@uwr.edu.pl) Tymoteusz Sawiński (Tymoteusz.sawinski@uwr.edu.pl)

3.2 Services provided by AMP – ACTRIS Poland Mobile LAB

SERVICE 1 – Access to services of the ACTRIS-Poland Mobile LAB In situ measurements	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service, Technical service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>AMP provides ground-based and airborne (hot-air balloon) atmospheric monitoring services, supporting scientific experiments and the testing of measurement devices, including: measuring particle sizes suspended in air within the 0.3–10 µm range; determining the concentration of collected particle fractions; measuring air temperature, pressure, and humidity; measuring ozone and soot concentrations; measuring the concentrations of atmospheric gasses such as CO₂, NO, NO₂, NH₃, SO₂, benzene, formaldehyde, and total volatile organic compounds (VOCs); collecting pollutant samples for chemical, biochemical, and crystallographic analyses in stationary laboratories; collecting and analyzing nanoparticles in the 10–300 nm range; and collecting and analyzing flora pollen, fungal spores, zooplankton, and microorganisms.</p> <p>AMP enables the examination of collected air pollutant samples, especially their morphology, chemical and phase composition, in order to determine their source.</p> <p>Use in SERVICE 2</p> <p>More information: https://us.edu.pl/en/nauka-i-badania/centra-badawcze/ulka/</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Remote / Physical

TARGET USERS	Academia, business sector and public sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Mariola Jabłońska (mariola.jablonska@us.edu.pl) Anna Abramowicz (anna.abramowicz@us.edu.pl)
SERVICE 2 - Access to services of the ACTRIS Poland Mobile Lab AMP remote sensing measurements	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service, Technical Service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	AMP offers atmospheric measurements using a mobile scanning lidar equipped with channels at 355S, 355P, 387, and 408 nm. More information: https://us.edu.pl/en/nauka-i-badania/centra-badawcze/ulka/
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Remote / Physical
TARGET USERS	Academia, business sector and public sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Mariola Jabłońska (mariola.jablonska@us.edu.pl) Anna Abramowicz (anna.abramowicz@us.edu.pl)

3.3 Services provided by the PACC – Prague Aerosol Calibration Centre

SERVICE 1 – Calibration of CPC	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research, Technical service, Training

SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>Calibration and operational checks for CPCs.</p> <p>CPC calibration includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the check of the main operational parameters (flows, temperatures, laser current, etc.), ● measurement of CPC counting efficiency (3-40 nm), ● check/adjustment of CPC cut-off diameter (10 nm for ACTRIS), ● measurement of CPC output linearity (1 000 - 50 000 #/ccm). <p>Training of operators for correct set-up and operation and basic maintenance of the CPCs.</p> <p>PACC is a new unit of CAIS-ECAC, but the hosting laboratory at ICPF CAS has a long lasting history in these measurements and is fully harmonized with WCCAP (TROPOS, Leipzig, Germany).</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Controlled
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, business sector and public sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Jakub Ondracek (ondracek@icpf.cas.cz)
SERVICE 2 – Calibration of MPSS	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research, Technical service, Training
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>Calibration and operational checks for MPSSs.</p> <p>MPSS calibration includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the check of the main status parameters (flows, HV, etc.), ● check of the recommended set-up (bipolar charger, sensors - RH/T&p in aerosol and sheath flow, positive polarity HV supply, flow ratio, etc.), ● sizing check (NIST latex particles 203 nm), ● plumbing time check (up- and down-scan), ● check/adjustment of the sheath flow, ● comparison of the particle number size distribution against reference instruments (MPSS and total count CPC) on atmospheric aerosol. <p>Training of operators for correct set-up and operation and basic maintenance of the MPSSs.</p>

	PACC is a new unit of CAIS-ECAC, but the hosting laboratory at ICPF CAS has a long lasting history in these measurements and is fully harmonized with WCCAP (TROPOS, Leipzig, Germany).
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient, controlled
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, business sector and public sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Jakub Ondracek (ondracek@icpf.cas.cz)
SERVICE 3 – Estimation of size resolved particle losses in the parts of sampling line	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research, Technical service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>Estimation of size resolved losses (penetration efficiency) of any parts of the sampling line.</p> <p>The measurement set-up allows for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • monodisperse testing aerosol (20-400 nm, salt solutions - usually ammonium sulphate, etc.), • penetration estimation up to 99.99999%, • built-in correction for the detector (CPC) inconsistency, • automated and fully controlled measurement process. <p>PACC is a new unit of CAIS-ECAC, but the hosting laboratory at ICPF CAS has a long lasting history in these measurements including testing of filtration efficiency of over 250 different types of PPE (Personal Protective Equipment) during COVID pandemic.</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Controlled
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, business sector and public sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Jakub Ondracek (ondracek@icpf.cas.cz)

SERVICE 4 – Technical audits of the microphysical measurements	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research, Technical service, Training
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>Offer of technical audits for the measurements stations and measurements set-up</p> <p>Compliance with ACTRIS standards (based on CEN/TS/best practice/decades of experience):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● sampling inlets, ● sampling lines, ● aerosol conditioning (drying), ● correct operation (parameters) of microphysical instruments. <p>Recommendations for improvements and possible arrangements in order to comply with standard operating procedures.</p> <p>PACC is a new unit of CAIS-ECAC, but the hosting laboratory at ICPF CAS has a long lasting history in aerosol measurements and in the last 3 years being also responsible for technical audits of ACTRIS AIS NFs.</p>
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient, controlled
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical, Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, business sector and public sector
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Jakub Ondracek (ondracek@icpf.cas.cz)

4 Training services developed in WP4

SERVICE – Young Scientists Training @AGORA	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Training school
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>Training through research of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> fundamental knowledge in novel, advanced techniques for measuring aerosol properties, covering in situ, remote sensing, and laboratory-based instruments. This training is performed by physical access. hands-on training for some novel aerosol instruments. This training is performed by physical access. small research projects under the supervision of experienced researchers. This training is performed by hybrid access. <p>More information at: https://atmosphere.ugr.es/informacion/presentacion/agora/training</p> <p>The service includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Administrative support to comply with internal procedures for accessing facilities (physical). Administrative and technical support for providing a workspace for visitors: desk space and internet access, meeting rooms, kitchen and lunch room (physical). Support for managing accommodation near UGR. Scientific support for supervision and analysis of collected data (physical, remote).
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient, controlled
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical and Remote
TARGET USERS	Academia, companies
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	Three weeks, once per year
TIME CONSTRAINTS	Early summer
CONTACT	Lucas Alados-Arboledas (alados@ugr.es)